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HEDGING AS A COMMUNICATIVE MANIPULATION STRATEGY

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One of the pragmatic strategies of political discourse is hedging. It is considered one of the strongest pragmatic means of impact on the listener or reader. This concept has been taken to linguistics from the fields of economics and insurance, where it is most widely used. Hedging in the economy means risk insurance intended to protect against various adverse events. The concept of hedging is relatively new in linguistics and little studied. Lakoff, was the first, who used this concept in his paper in 1970. The paper is called "Hedges: A Study in Meaning Criteria and the Logic of Fuzzy Concepts." It is interesting, but Lakoff does not consider the communicative function of hedging in his article. He pays particular attention to the logical features of the following words: manner of speaking, largely, rather, and others. Hedge in the artistic sense means 'obstacle', 'obstruction'. Being multidimensional, hedge as an element of hedging combines several factors: pragmatic, semantic and cognitive. [1]

However, it was L. Zadeh who first described the concept of hedging in his works. He did not use the concept of "hedging" itself, he called this phenomenon fuzzy set theory when modeling the structure of any language. According to this theory, blurring appears when the definition of a word from any category is considered accurate only to a certain point. As a result, Zadeh writes that the concepts of any natural language have very vague boundaries, so the speaker's suggestions can be false, and if they are true, only up to a certain point or false up to a certain point. [2]

Weireich then studied hedging in 1966. He did not use the word "hedging" in describing this term either. In his work "On the semantic structure of English" he spoke of the metalinguistic operator. W. Weireich writes that each language uses its own metalanguage to simplify purposes. For meta operators, it includes words like true, assumed, actual, and others.[3]

V. Namsaraev for the first time considers hedging as an independent phenomenon. He writes that many linguists regard this concept in the context of other linguistic phenomena, such as modality, methodological discourse, strategies of politeness. V. Namsaraev considers hedging as a "pragmatic category that

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performs the protective transformation of the proposition and includes linguistic means that function at the level of interpersonal communication". [4]

By using hedging in the speech, the authors and speakers try to eliminate the absolute accuracy of their statement. They are trying to protect themselves from criticism. Therefore, it can be argued that the concept of coverage can and should be considered as an independent concept, since it is used to achieve this goal.

Hedges are a means of expressing vagueness. This concept is characterized by vagueness, uncertainty, but it definitely does not mean something bad. Pragmatic coverage studies have been traced back to the 1980s. In communication, speakers tend to express themselves vaguely, deliberately using evasiveness in order not to be assertive and to make their words seem more polite. Hedges like "more or less", "to some extent", "somewhat", "quite a bit", "fully", "more or less", "really", and "almost" are effective if you want to be polite to your listeners in conversations.

E. Prince divides hedges into two classes, which include shields and approximators. The first group of hedges show how accurate the speaker's attitude towards the proposal is, the second group of hedges indicate the authenticity of the entire proposal. The proposed hedges include the following words and expressions: kind of, something, a little, absolutely describable as, some, etc. [5]

Hedging is a pragmatic phenomenon, and its interpretation depends on the context. Practically, any linguistic unit can function as a hedge depending on pragmatic factors: - I think it's a bit weird (I think is a hedge); - I think of you all the time (think is not a hedge). [6] Hedges cannot be assigned to a specific grammatical class. They can be expressed by syntactic, morphological and lexical means. The following hedges are distinguished in English: modal verbs (may, might, can, could, would, should); modal words (adjectives: likely, a / probable, possible; nouns: statement, suggestion, supposition, estimation, possibility; adverbs: possibly, perhaps, practically, probably, presumably, likely, apparently, virtually); approximators of time, degree, quantity and frequency; epistemic verbs (argue, suppose, believe, estimate, suggest, think, indicate); introductory phrases and expressions (as far as we know, it is our opinion that, I think, we feel that); conditional subordinate sentences (if true, if anything); tag questions (... , isn't it?); negative constructions (no...?); passive-impersonal constructions (it could be suggested).[6]

However, the role of hedges in sentences is not always positive. Inappropriate use can have negative consequences on communication. This happens mainly in cases where precise information is required, so the blur encountered by the hedges will be inappropriate and can lead to communication failures. Therefore, it can be

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concluded that the use of politically correct vocabulary is relevant today. The politically correct vocabulary is expressed through hedging, which main function is also mitigation or softening.

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